

A Potentiometric Study on the Complexes of Gadolinium, Erbium and Ytterbium in Aqueous Solution

S. U. LAKHANI, G. S. THAKUR and S. P. SANGAL

Laxminarayan Institute of Technology,
Nagpur University, Nagpur-440 010

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Fig. 1. Titration curves of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphaphenazole.

From the titration curves, $\bar{n}$ and pL values for metal-ligand systems were also determined. From the curves ($\bar{n}$ vs pL) $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were determined by half integral method. In the cases of La^{3+} , Y^{3+} , Gd^{3+} complexes, the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was found to be less than 1.78 log units; these were computed by least square method and are reported in Table 1.

TABLE-1

t=25°		$\mu=0.1M$					
Cations	H ⁺	La ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Gd ³⁺	Dy ³⁺	Y ³⁺
log K ₁	7.88	7.45	7.4	6.87	6.64	5.08	4.91
log K ₂	-	4.52	-	4.80	4.61	-	4.61

The order of stability of metal chelates is found to be $La^{3+} > Pr^{3+} > Nd^{3+} > Gd^{3+} > Dy^{3+} > Y^{3+}$.

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THE stability of complex ion or a molecule in a solution is determined by the nature of the central atom and the addends. The most important characteristics of the central atom determining the stability of the complex compounds are the degree of oxidation (the charge of the central ion in case of ionic complexes), the dimensions (ionic radii) and the electronic configuration. From this point of view rare earth metal ions form an interesting group which consist of similar electronic configuration and the trivalent oxidation state. Thus, in the present study the effect of ionic radii and various ligands containing oxygen and nitrogen as donor atoms have been carried out. In previous publications some lower group of rare earth series have been studied¹⁻⁵. In the present paper the rare earths under study are trivalent gadolinium, erbium and ytterbium using the following organic ligands:

- 7-Iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (IOSA)
- 8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (OSA)
- 1,2-Dihydroxybenzene (pyrocatechol, PYC)
- 2,3-Dihydroxynaphthalene-6-sulphonic acid (DHNSA)
- 1,2-Dihydroxybenzene-3,5-disulphonic acid (Trivial name Tiron)

Experimental

Chemicals: All the chemicals used were of AnalaR Grade. Stock solutions (0.01 M) of IOSA, OSA, PYC (E. Merck); DHNSA, Tiron (Fluka, A.G.) were freshly prepared in double distilled carbon dioxide free water. The rare earth solutions were prepared by dissolving rare earth metal trioxide (Johnson and Matthey) in minimum quantity of perchloric acid and standardized by complexometric method⁶.

Instruments: A pH meter (Toshniwal CAT No. CL-43 Type) with combined glass-calomel electrode assembly was used to obtain pH of solutions during the titration. Nitrogen gas was passed continuously during the course of titration. The titration cell was immersed in an electronically controlled thermostatic bath maintained at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The contents of the cell were continuously stirred during the titration. The pH meter was calibrated against standard buffers.

Results and Discussion

Irving-Rossotti's pH titration technique⁷ has been adopted for the evaluation of "proton-ligand" and "metal-ligand" stability constants at 35° and ionic strength 0.2 M (NaClO₄). One or more of the following computational methods have been used to evaluate the stability constants: (a) interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values, (b) linear extrapolation method, (c) elimination method and (d) mid-point method. Tables 1 and 2 give the values of proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants, respectively.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT 35° AND $\mu = 0.2 M$ (NaClO₄)

Ligand	log K ₁ ^H		log K ₂ ^H		log B ^H	
	A	B	A	B	A	B
IOSA	7.01	7.02	2.60	2.61	9.61	9.63
OSA	8.07	8.06	3.80	3.81	11.87	11.87
PYC	—	11.61(c)	9.05	9.08	20.69(b,c)	20.42(d)
DHNSA	—	11.40(c)	7.97	7.98	19.38(b,c)	19.4 (d)
Tiron	—	12.21(d)	7.59	7.59	19.8 (b,d)	19.8 (d)

TABLE 2—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT 35° AND $\mu = 0.2 M$ (NaClO₄)

Ligand (L)	log K _{Gd-L}		log K _{Er-L}		log K _{Yb-L}	
	A	B	A	B	A	B
IOSA	6.07	6.08	6.13	6.13	6.33	6.35
OSA	6.56	6.60	6.64	6.65	6.86	6.86
PYC	9.60	9.57	—	9.87	—	10.28
DHNSA	10.10	10.13	10.18	10.17	10.46	10.49
Tiron	13.38	13.37	13.81	13.80	14.05	13.99

All the ligands under investigation are bidentate and form stable five membered rings during complexation. The order of stability constants in terms of the various ligands under study was found to follow the order IOSA < OSA < PYC < DHNSA < Tiron (Fig. 1). Both IOSA and OSA coordinate through phenoxide O atom and quinoline N atom.

Fig. 1. Variation of stability constants of rare earths with various organic ligand.

In case of PYC, DHNSA and Tiron, two phenoxide O atoms at *ortho* positions are acting as donor atoms. Thus, it is observed that in the above ligands, where two phenoxide O atoms are present, they form more stable complexes as compared to

the ligands containing only one phenoxide O atom and one quinoline N atom as donors.

The donor atoms and chelating ring structure formed with the same metal ion are identical both in IOSA and OSA, but in the case of IOSA molecule, the presence of an electron withdrawing iodo group as compared to OSA (the iodo group decreases the basicity of IOSA compared to OSA) may result in lower stability. Such a trend has also been observed by Pujari and Munshi⁸ in the case of yttrium chelates. Tiron has the highest stability which might be due to two sulphonate groups which increase the reactivity of phenoxide groups towards coordination⁹⁻¹⁰. DHNSA is next to Tiron and has higher stability as compared to PYC. This might be due to the presence of naphthalenering¹⁰.

Fig. 2 shows the variation in the values of stability constant of rare earths with ionic radii. It has been observed that the value of the stability constants follow the trend Gd(III) < Er(III) < Yb(III) which is identical with the general trend shown by trivalent lanthanoids with majority of aminopolycarboxylic acids¹¹.

Fig. 2. Variation of stability constants of rare earths with ionic radii.

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